

UTILIZING COGNITIVE AND DISCURSIVE PERSPECTIVES IN THE EXAMINATION OF ARTISTIC WORKS

Albina Bazarbaeva

DSC, Associate Professor, Department of the Teaching English methodology-3,
Uzbekistan state university of world languages, Uzbekistan

E-mail: babai77700@list.ru

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Annotation

The notions of “concept” and “discourse” significantly shape the nature of modern linguistics, including cognitive linguistics. The study of discourse as an abstract model of language activity becomes a fruitful method for uncovering high-level concepts that reflect knowledge about the world and language in consciousness. The study of the cognitive space of the artistic text on the basis of linguophilosophical concepts and ideas reveals the significance of the role of the linguistic personality as a subject of speech activity. This includes analysing the formation and perception of speech and deciphering the cognitive structures underlying the perception and interpretation of artistic works.

Key words: concept, discourse, cognitive structure, cognitive space, cognitive-discursive analysis, semantic perceptions.

The method, based on linguophilosophical principles, allows for a deeper understanding of the relationship between language, thinking and artistic form of expression, opening new perspectives for the study of linguistic and cultural dynamics in texts and their perception. In addition, the philosophical category of activity, encompassing human cognitive and speech activities and the basic concepts of cognitive linguistics are taken into account. These aspects help to reveal the mechanisms of meaning formation and text perception through the prism of cognitive processes. To fully investigate the cognitive aspect of a fiction text, it is necessary to take into account not only theories of discourse, communication and speech impact, but also scholarly debates about the structure of spoken dialogue, linguistic text analysis and the organisation of lexical word meaning. Understanding the diversity of perspectives in the field emphasises the importance of having an integrated approach or tool that can meet the diverse requirements of the research. This will make it possible to reveal more deeply and fully the processes of text meaning formation and its impact on the reader.

Elements in the style of artistic speech appear in a processed, standardised and selected form. They are not used in their natural form; the use of non-literal words in their original form can lead to the cluttering of the language, which does not contribute to its enrichment and the development of literary norms. As V.V. Vinogradov, in fiction the national language with its unique grammar and diverse vocabulary is used as a tool and a form of artistic creation.

In other words, all aspects of the common language, including its grammatical structure, vocabulary, system of meanings and semantics, act here as tools for artistic abstract recreation and illumination of socio-cultural reality [Vinogradov, 1963].

Consequently, the main task of artistic speech is to contribute to the embodiment of the author's intention and ideas, to reveal a deeper meaning to the reader through the use of linguistic stylistic means.

Cognitive-discourse analysis of text presents discourse as an abstraction that goes beyond its concrete manifestations, considered as material for the construction of generalised patterns of language use. In this study, the emphasis is on the analysis of abstract-logical concepts defined by general patterns of consciousness and thinking. Simultaneously with this approach, the notion of “concept” in the context of text analysis appears.

A concept in the context of a text is seen as a key element that contributes to the formation and expression of new knowledge, acting as a source of stimulation for cognition. “Text concept” embodies the deep meaning of the object of cognition, being a hidden structure of meanings. Text, in its turn, is considered as a form of communication and a materialised result of speech-thought activity, which creates a natural environment for the expression and existence of the concept in its verbal form related to the socio-historical setting.

According to L.R. Gataullina's statement, linguistic ability is considered as a manifestation of general cognitive mechanisms, which implies the possibility of studying various aspects of human nature through language - its thinking, memory, cognitive processes. Linguistic analysis is not limited only to the description of linguistic behaviour, but beyond that, it includes the analysis of relevant mental states and processes. The main goal is to create a unified model explaining how linguistic knowledge is organised in humans and how they use it in the generation and perception of speech [Gataullina, 2005].

Within the framework of artistic concepts we can distinguish two main categories: typical concepts and individual-authorial concepts. However, it is worth noting that even typical concepts in an artistic text acquire a unique authorial embodiment.

Since the consciousness of the author and the reader interact at the level of associations, which forms the basis for speech and thinking activity, and, in addition, provides text regulation, influencing the reader and directing his perception, an effective method of analysing textual concepts is the study of associative links in the text and the creation of associative-semantic fields of concepts on their basis [Pankratova, 2009].

From which we can conclude that in the study of the concept using the cognitive-stylistic approach, based on the analysis of linguistic phenomena through cognitive-discourse analysis, the emphasis is placed on the primacy of the text in the structure of discourse. Different types of discourses, conditioned by sociocultural and stylistic factors, serve as a context for the formation of such relevant concepts as scientific, artistic, media. The study of communicative and cognitive peculiarities of the functioning of these varieties of textual concepts is an urgent task to be solved within the framework of various approaches in modern linguistics, including aspects of communicative text stylistics.

Modern cognitive linguistics actively applies interpretive strategies that take into account not only the characteristics of a particular utterance and the general body of knowledge, but also pay special attention to the personal aspects of the interpreter and his/her subjective perception of the text in his/her own mental space. Justification allows a deeper and more complete understanding of the processes of interpretation and perception of the text, taking into account the individual characteristics of each reader or researcher. The approach is justified because in real life the uniqueness of the author's and reader's personalities excludes a complete coincidence of their semantic perceptions.

The author's freedom in choosing interpretative solutions, individual approaches to text enrichment and differences in the reader's linguistic, cultural upbringing and ethical

experience may vary considerably. For this purpose, modern linguistics applies cognitive-discursive analysis in the analysis of a fiction text, which is not limited to the consideration of the text only from linguistic positions, but in addition, takes into account extra-linguistic factors.

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